

Synthesis and characterization of (1-x) BaTiO₃ – xCoFe₂O₄ - Multiferroic composite

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Abstract

Recently, much attention has been paid to the investigation of multiferroic composite materials which have a combination of two or more materials with ferroelectric (e.g., BaTiO₃ and PbTiO₃), ferromagnetic (e.g., CoFe₂O₄ and NiFe₂O₄) and show magnetoelectric (ME) coupling effect [1]. These materials are attractive because they offer the possibility to control the polarization by a magnetic field or the magnetization by an electric field. The coupling effects provide multiferroic composites in the applications like electro-magnetic interference filters, capacitors, transducers, and integral chip inductors [2-4]. In present study, (1-x) BaTiO₃ – xCoFe₂O₄ (x=0.00, 0.05, 0.15) ceramics have been synthesized by a solid-state reaction route. Formation of the composite with two separate (BaTiO₃ – CoFe₂O₄) phases have been identified by X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis. The leakage current density (J-E) is found to be increased with the increase of CoFe₂O₄ concentration while varying at different electric field.

An enhancement of magnetization with increasing CoFe₂O₄ concentration has been observed at room temperature magnetization studies using vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM). Polarization versus electric field (P-E) hysteresis loops show that, the ferroelectric properties decreases with increasing CoFe₂O₄ content. Further, the temperature dependent dielectric constant measured for BTO/CFO ceramic samples at different frequencies and magneto electric coupling studies have also been performed. The details of the results will be presented and discussed.

Keywords: Multiferroic, BTO/CFO, Magneto –dielectric, solid state reaction.

References

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